

Monochromatic LED cube by Arduino Microcontroller

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Abstract

The “Monochromatic LED cube by Arduino Microcontroller” was focused for teaching aid, training kit and the decorative elements in the ceremonies. The system was mainly comprised Arduino Uno, LEDs and some resistors. It was used monochromatic 4 x 4 x 4 LED matrix. The cube was consisted of 64 green LEDs which made up 16 vertical LED rows and 4 horizontal layers. The output of the system displayed various pattern designs. The controlled program source code can be derived the LEDs to show various patterns. This program was written in the Arduino programming language, debugged, compiled and burnt into the ATmega 328P microcontroller by using the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE).

Keywords: Arduino Uno, monochromatic LED, ATmega 328P

Introduction

Nowadays, LED cube is the next generation display piece of art and are adored among the electronic enthusiasts around the globe. LED cube is a set of components that can produce display of animation on the LED assembled part. The suitable software and hardware that will be involved that are important characteristics to take account about it. There are several different designs of Arduino board which was introduced in 2005. These are intended for different types of applications. They can all be programmed from the same Arduino development software. The C or C++ language program is interfaced with Arduino through serial communication.

In this research, the design and construction of various patterns of monochromatic 4×4×4 LED cube by Arduino microcontroller is constructed. The constructed LED cube contains four layers. Each layer has sixteen LEDs and total four layers have altogether sixty-four LEDs. So, the LED cube contains four rows and sixteen columns. The display panel of this circuit is 64 LEDs. This circuit is designed to display various pattern designs, including lattice plane in the cubic crystal structures. To control the functions of the cube circuit, Arduino microcontroller is used in this research. The block diagram of the system is shown in Figure 1.

Arduino Processing Unit

The system used Arduino 1.8.10 version. The control program is written in Arduino C programming language. The software is the IDE software very similar to a word-processor, but can send the Arduino program (or ‘sketch’) to the microcontroller. The first thing in this project is to build the LED cube and to make sure the array must follow the desired model of a LED cube. Next, the Arduino Uno will be the microcontroller and will control the LED array by using multiplexer circuit. The photograph of Arduino IDE processing can see the Figure 2. The flowchart diagram of the system is shown in Figure 3.

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Figure. 1 The block diagram of LED cube controlled system

Figure. 2 The photograph of Arduino IDE software

Construction of the System

The wires were made connections to each of the 4 horizontal layers and the wire down routed through the holes alongside the LED. These wires will be used with the cathode/layer control. The way to connect the bottom of the grid has a method to the madness. The Layer 1 wire connects to pin 1 of the cathode control header, all the way up to pin 4 connecting to layer 4's black wire. The leads of the cable wire and get some solder on the bottom of the LEDs and one-by-one connect each of the 4 rows of LEDs to a connector. The LED cube is made up of cathode columns and anode layers. The cathode legs of every LED in a layer are soldered one layer to another. All the anode legs in one column are soldered one LED to another. The photograph of the construction of the LED cube is shown in Figure 4 to 12 step by step. The circuit connection of the LED cube is Figure 13.

Program Listing of the System

Figure. 3 The flowchart diagram of the system

Figure. 4 The diagram of LED cube template

Figure. 5 Photograph of the format plate to get fixed position of each LED

Figure. 6 Photograph of the constructed one layer on the template

Figure. 7 Photograph of the constructed half of the one layer for LED cube

Figure. 8 Photograph of the constructed one layer for LED cube

Figure. 9 Photograph of the constructed two layers for LED cube

Figure. 10 Photograph of the constructed three layers for LED cube

Figure. 11 Photograph of the constructed four layers for LED cube

Figure. 12 Photograph of the top view of the LED cube

Figure. 13 The circuit connection of the 4x4x4 LED cube

Operation of the System

When the +5V power supply applied to the system, all LEDs are simultaneously turned on in the cube. And then all LEDs turned off and will blink to and fro before beginning to display other patterns in the demonstration mode. Once all sixteen patterns of the system have been run step by step, the process will start all over again until the power is switched off. The system has 64 LEDs in a monochromatic (green color) 4 x 4 x 4 LED matrix. Four LEDs each across length, width and height. Each of the 4 layers contains 16 LEDs. Physical Dimension of the system is approximately 8cm x 8cm x 8cm, consecutive LEDs are separated by 2.54cm. The complete circuit diagram of the system is Figure 14.

Figure. 14 The complete circuit diagram of the system

Figure. 15 Photograph of the top view of the complete circuit

Figure. 16 Photograph of the side view of the complete circuit

Results

The “Arduino Based LED cube” is successfully constructed. The system is a 16 x 4 multiplexed display on the LED cube. It requires 16 vertical LED rows and 4 horizontal layers. So the total required I/O pins of Arduino are 20. It contains 64 LEDs and LED current limit per layer is 160 mA. This power supply system is used 5V, 0.5A power bank. The power consumption of the system is about 3W (10mA x 16 x 4 x 5V). The dimension of the LED cube is 8x8x8 cubic centimeters and it is constructed by 4-row (layers) and 16-column. The top view and side view of the complete circuit are shown in Figure 15 to 16.

Discussion and Conclusion

The constructed system is low cost. The constructed technique of LED cube is very interested. The system can be used Arduino Uno board. An LED cube does not make a 6x7x8, or even oddly shaped ones. The green color is used in this system because it's forward voltage is 1.9 V to 4.0 V and the constructed cube is brighter than other. The various patterns of displays are produced by controlling the column and layer selection. To do this work, the controlled program is used as layer and column selectors. The various pattern designs are also produced by C programming source codes and this source codes are uploaded to Arduino microcontroller and then the system starts to run. The display pattern can be 3D- graphics LED display, 2D- graphics LED display, various pattern of blinking LEDs and light decoration based on the Arduino source codes. This circuit is very useful for the students, electronic hobbyists and electrician. The system can be modified by controlling the voice by using RGB LEDs and crystal lattice for material science in the future.

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